

Accounts of Apartheid's Bloody Past and Psychological Damage:

Magical Realism in Zoë Wicomb's David's Story

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Abstract: In *David's Story*, Zoë Wicomb depicts some of the violence that occurred in the anti-apartheid movement, including rape and sexual and physical torture of female cadres in the ANC (African National Congress) recruiting and training camps. By demonstrating scenes that have been concealed and covered up, bringing them out into the open and a step closer to the truth, and by creating a counter or alternative history from the perspective of the oppressed black people, particularly black women. Wicomb attempts to remember forgotten women's bodies in colonial history, detecting the origin of their silencing and their unrecognised resistance. Furthermore, by using materials from a dubiously documented South African past, the novel turns the past into a narrative not entirely to itself but fractured, non-linear, self-critical and even self-mocking. In addition, by reproducing the figure of a vulnerable female body and by showing the gendered dehumanisation during apartheid, Wicomb reinforces the fact that apartheid is not only racial but also gendered. Linking Saartjie Baartman with Dulcie and demonstrating the subjugation and oppression of South African women makes it possible for David to associate the oppression of these women with his own story and trauma, pointing at how the coloured community has been victimised through colonisation and racial oppression.

INTRODUCTION

In *David's Story*, Zoë Wicomb depicts sexual and physical torture of female cadres in the ANC recruiting and training camps during the anti-apartheid struggle. Aligning with Zakes Mda, she points out the evils of the anti-apartheid movement and presents a deromanticised version of it. Through her unreliable narrator, Wicomb attempts to unearth concealed and buried truths about the movement. She thereby creates a counter or alternative history from the perspective of the oppressed black people, particularly black women. Dulcie's appalling story cannot be told or disclosed not only because it has a ghastly effect

on David but also because it troubles the apparently glorious records of the anti-apartheid struggle. By showing the gendered dehumanisation during apartheid, Wicomb reinforces the fact that apartheid is not only racial but also gendered. Since the traditional realist narrative is not fully equipped to convey or reveal the ineffable stories of Dulcie, Wicomb introduces a fragmentary and repetitive narrative with two parallel stories, employs African traditions, rituals and magic, and, most importantly, brings back the ghost of Dulcie to serve her purpose.

David's Story has two plot lines: one is set in 1991 and deals with the anti-apartheid guerrillas and the other is set at the beginning of the 20th century and deals with the Griqua community. According to Giuliana Iannaccaro, dealing with the history of the Khoi peoples of Southern Africa (especially the Griqua) and the marginalised position of colouredness in the apartheid state, the novel avoids the conflict between the black and the white in order to probe more subtle social and political conflicts (Iannaccaro 2015, 43). In searching for his origins and justifying his role as a revolutionary, David tries to record his life story in written form and thus hires a female amanuensis. The character of Dulcie—David's fellow revolutionary—is complex because she does not speak for herself, but is rather always suggested or remembered by someone else, mainly by David and the amanuensis. By showing the dominance of men over, and the sexual torture of, women, the novel reveals the gendered violence within the freedom movement, exposes the evil of it, and thus deromanticises and demystifies it.

“A KIND OF SCREAM SOMEHOW ECHOING THROUGH MY STORY”: RISKS AND DIFFICULTIES IN DEPICTING DULCIE

David Dirkse, a former MK guerrilla, attempts to recount the story of his life to an amanuensis, which focuses on his unsuccessful relationship with his fellow female guerrilla Dulcie Oliphant. From David's fragmented information, we can assume that Dulcie was a distinguished military officer in the anti-apartheid movement. However, Dulcie is depicted as “the necessary silence in the text; she can't be fleshed out precisely because of her shameful treatment which those committed to the Movement would rather not talk about” (Meyer and Olver 2002, 190–191). According to Shane Graham (2008), having attempted and failed to describe Dulcie's role in his story, David decides to change her by concentrating on the figure of Saartjie Baartman and the Khoi woman named Krotoä (130). Graham (2008) goes on to say, “Both women's stories become ur-texts of a sort for the situation of women in David's life—in other words, they are phantoms whose later incarnations include Dulcie, the narrator, and David's wife Sally” (130). By saying this, Graham actually links women who suffered during apartheid with women who suffered from colonisation, and asserts that the victimisation of women in South Africa is deeply rooted in time.

Seeing David's troubled and confused mind about Dulcie, the narrator advises him “to displace her by working on the historical figure of Saartjie Baartman instead” (Wicomb 2001, 134). Since David refuses to answer most of the questions regarding Dulcie, the narrator feels that she must place all the snippets together

as meticulously as she can and imagine the entire story. She even considers “Dulcie [...] a decoy. She does not exist in the real world; David has invented her in order to cover up aspects of his own story” (2001, 124). On the contrary, Graham (2008) points out that for David it is Dulcie’s corporeality—the materiality of her body and the atrocities perpetrated on it—that makes her story so essentially ineffable (132).

David wants the story to be written by an amanuensis but he is not able to talk about Dulcie at all. Regarding David’s need to have an amanuensis, the narrator says in the “Preface”, “He wanted me to write it, not because he thought that his story could be written by someone else, but rather because it would no longer belong to him. In other words, he both wanted and did not want it to be written” (Wicomb 2001, 1). This quotation clearly expresses David’s desire and at the same time reluctance to write about Dulcie. He gives the narrator a page which she describes as “a mess of scribbles and scoring out and doodling of peculiar figures that cannot be reproduced here” (2001, 135). Seeing these scribbles, the amanuensis gets lost and realises that it is not possible to “cast Dulcie and the events surrounding her as a story” (2001, 150). In supporting the amanuensis, Dorothy Driver (2001) explains: “For David, Dulcie remains at a stage of unrepresentability, not least because certain aspects of her treatment cannot be faced, since facing them would force him to confront his own past not only as victim but also as victimiser” (232). His (sense of) victimisation stems from racial subjugation and resulting colouredness, and his role as a perpetrator arises from his alleged involvement in Dulcie’s physical and sexual torture. The duality of being both a victim and perpetrator demonstrates the multiple selves of David, and signifies the complexity of trauma under such conditions.

David describes Dulcie as a woman with “legendary activities” (Wicomb 2001, 125) and “her quiet, forceful manner, the way in which even the old people echoed her words and nodded” (2001, 128). Although David wants to write about Dulcie, he shows his unwillingness in revealing information about the anti-apartheid movement. David subsequently realises that “truth is too large a thing even for those who take on vast projects like changing the world, that it can only be handled in tit-bits” (2001, 141). Instead, there is the ‘trurt’, which cannot be understood but can only be memorised like “a half-remembered Latin lesson” (2001, 136): “TRURT ... TRURT ... TRURT ... TRURT ... the trurt in the black and white ... colouring the truth to say that ... which cannot be said the thing of no name ...” (2001, 136). Wicomb’s statement indicates the difficulties and, to some extent, the impossibilities of representing truth in language since language is subjective and manipulative, and thus produces more than one version of truth. Throughout the novel, several magical realist elements—non-linear narrative, parallelism, myth and magic, and, most importantly, ghosts—are used by the author to unsettle any reliable access to the truth and to advocate the possibility of the existence of many versions of truth. Loocke (2008) says, ultimately, that David gives up on the truth and “is especially troubled by the concept of ‘false memory’” (45). According to Laub (1995), it is indeed very common that “[those] who do not tell their story become victims of a distorted memory [...]. The longer

the story remains untold, the more distorted it becomes in the [person's] conception of it, so much so that the [he/she] doubts the reality of the actual events" (64). Laub's statement highlights the distortion of memory or story over time. Here, even the narrator becomes doubtful of her story.

Since David fails to reveal all the necessary information, the amanuensis has to speculate to write the story and at times give her own views. Thus, whatever she writes might be unreliable. Again, the freedom to write someone else's story allows her to use her imagination and thus provide us with a different version of David and Dulcie's life story, and an alternative history of the anti-apartheid struggle by revealing its lacking. Since Dulcie cannot be represented, it is not possible for the narrator and thus the reader to know more about her. It can also be said in the opposite way: since it is not possible to know more about Dulcie, she cannot be represented. She remains more like a spirit or "a protean subject that slithers hither and thither, out of reach, repeating, replacing, transforming itself" (Wicomb 2001, 35). Despite acknowledging the fact that Dulcie is "a kind of scream somehow echoing through my story" (2001, 134), David says that "even if a full story were to be figured out by someone, it would be a story that cannot be told, that cannot be translated into words, into language we use for everyday matters" (2001, 151). It can be deduced from the above quotation that Wicomb is advocating a special type of narrative or language significantly different from what we use in everyday conversation. This type of narrative should have the potential to penetrate the walls of traumatic events and to bring unimaginable and untold stories to light.

Wicomb seems to have considered the freedom struggle an evil, however a lesser one compared to apartheid. By exposing the evil of the movement, she seems to be saying that the movement fails to fulfil its target, and instead facilitates discord among black people. Since David is unwilling and/or unable to expose stories about Dulcie, and the amanuensis' speculation and invention of Dulcie is not sufficient to write a story, Wicomb brings back the ghost of Dulcie and lets her reveal her own story. The appearance and acceptance of Dulcie's ghost in the narrative defies the scientific logic or order, and underpins the employment of the magical realist narrative. Magical realism in the novel, thus, provides the subaltern (here, women) a means to make their voices heard.

In "Can the Subaltern Speak?" Gayatri Spivak (1988) states that "[i]f in the context of colonial production, the subaltern has no history and cannot speak, the subaltern as female is even more deeply in shadow" (287). Her statement refers to the double victimisation of women. The female amanuensis is certainly frustrated by this dilemma and thus poses the question: "Will I never know what's going on? Does no one care what I think? Will I ever be heard above the rude buzz of the blue bottles?" (Wicomb 2001, 213). Being asked by the narrator concerning the reason behind Dulcie's silence, David replies: "Belief. Pride. Pride in belief. The virus of secrecy" (2001, 204). Dulcie's refusal to speak up is directly associated with her sense of oppression and victimisation. She does not want to ascend the military hierarchy because she knows that doing so will not only

endanger her self-identity but could ultimately cause fatal opposition from her male comrades.

Shane Graham (2008) believes that the narrator's account of Dulcie is probably made up, even fantastic, but it is notable for the importance it places on her physical body, particularly on "the scars on her back" (132). The image of the "criss-cross cuts on each of her naturally bolstered buttocks" (Wicomb 2001, 19) provokes traumatic memories that she cannot forget. According to Driver (2001), Dulcie is the "unrepresentable body in pain [which] absorbs and gives back the threats and promises of a violently oppressive and violently revolutionary past, a past that has not yet quite passed" (218). By saying this, Driver actually sheds light on the cruel colonial past of South Africa and its intrusion into the present, and demands a possible way to overcome it. She also finds an association between the representation of Baartman and Dulcie's body. Bodies thus become a manifestation of the nation: Baartman and Dulcie's violated bodies stand for the devastated condition of South Africa under colonisation and apartheid respectively and can be considered a part of South African national historiography. Mary Douglas (1973) asserts, "[T]he human body is always treated as an image of society and [...] there can be no natural way of considering the body that does not involve at the same time a social dimension" (98). By saying so, Douglas associates the human body with society and thus finds the social dimension of the human body. The act of associating disfigured bodies with the nation as a whole alludes to *Midnight's Children* where Saleem resembles the nation, his birth parallels the emergence of independent India and Pakistan, and he embodies the pain, uncertainty and identity crisis of a newborn nation and becomes a microcosm of post-independence India.

WAR AND SEXUAL VIOLENCE: REPRODUCING THE VULNERABLE FEMALE BODY

Just like David, Dulcie is a soldier of the MK—the military wing of the ANC—where she was revered for her legendary military prowess. Loocke (2008) argues that since South Africa is a patriarchal society where women are restricted to the traditional roles of wife and mother, Dulcie's fellow male guerrillas could not tolerate their inclusion in the army and thus showed them what they considered to be their rightful and apposite place through rape and other forms of sexual torture (26). Regarding Dulcie's silence, Loocke (2008) states, "Her absence draws attention to the other absences, such as the experiences of all those female ANC members, and it also challenges our understanding of language as a means to represent reality" (26). Dulcie and her trauma can never be expressed through our everyday language or in a linear traditional narrative, and that is why Wicomb uses two parallel fragmentary narratives, employs African mythical and historical figures, and, most significantly, brings Dulcie's ghost back to life.

It is striking that what seems to be important and is acknowledged in the novel is completely absent in South African history. Stories of sexual torture and rape during the anti-apartheid movement can be found in public discourse but are

completely absent in the nation's collective history. By exposing the violence Dulcie underwent during the movement and by giving her a voice, Wicomb allows all the tortured and marginalised women in the history of South Africa to depict their untranslatable trauma. Since David fails to expose all the events of Dulcie's life, the female narrator has to imagine and speculate to write the story. By giving the amanuensis the freedom to imagine, Wicomb emphasises the notion of the unreliability of a single or absolute version of truth and advocates the existence of many versions of truth beyond our own—a significant feature of magical realism.

David's Story strives to do what the TRC hearings attempted to do but failed. Through a fragmentary narrative, the inclusion of African traditions, beliefs and rituals and the presence of ghosts, David's Story attempts to discover the veiled history of the TRC. By striving to create a story out of silence, Wicomb attempts to reveal the dehumanising treatment of women, show what is lacking in official historiography, and find a way to get closer to the truth. Mengel (2009) proposes that truth or reality can only be narrated through "indirection, approximation, circumlocution or substitution [and] by simultaneously reflecting on the difficulty of coming to terms with it [...] to express the inexpressible, to speak about the unspeakable" (315). However, I think there are also devices of magical realism that speak the unspeakable.

Although the novel sets out to write about Dulcie, it hints at the potential difficulties and risks of doing so. Meg Samuelson (2007) remarks that the novel "is keenly aware of the powers and dangers of representation and of what is risked in writing about women in the war zone and its aftermath: a representational minefield in which women are cast as idealized warriors, silenced victims, and emblems of the domestic world toward which the male warrior ostensibly directs his efforts" (835). Samuelson's statement refers to the difficulties of writing about women who are always directed by the males. In other words, giving a literary representation of Dulcie's tortured body also risks inflicting more torture on her body. As Mike Marais (2005) notes, "Dulcie cannot be represented in language, because it is in and through language that the body of the black woman has been dismembered by being reduced to a vocabulary of signs" (28).

There are some scenes of Dulcie's physical, sexual and psychological torture committed by her fellow male guerrillas:

The men in balaclavas come like privileged guests into her bedroom, in the early hours, always entering the house by different routes, ridiculing her reinforced bolts and locks, the secret code of her Securilarm system. ... Now, they come without a sound [...]. Then she arranges herself on her back with her eyes open, her hands folded behind her head, looking straight ahead at the door. ... One of them carries a doctor's Gladstone bag filled with peculiar instruments and electrical leads. (Wicomb 2001, 81-82)

The above quotation refers to the intimidating presence of the male anti-apartheid guerrillas in ANC training camps, and the helplessness of female

guerrillas and the passive acceptance of their own suffering. I agree with Pipic's observation that "one of them is carrying a doctor's bag with instruments implies that Dulcie might have been the victim of sexual torture" (Pipic 2017, 197). Dulcie understands the fact that "fucking women was a way of preventing them from rising in the Movement" (Wicomb 2001, 179) and that it is "this unspoken part of a girl's training" (2001, 123) that has not been revealed in the TRC hearings. The history of the anti-apartheid movement is all about the marginalisation of black people; however, Wicomb probes deep into the movement, exposes the double victimisation of women within it and in this way provides us with a more marginalised version of it.

Concerning the issue of fully addressing the violence perpetrated against women during the TRC hearings, Joyce Seroke said, "We only began to scratch the surface" of the violence against women, but still there were piles of "gruesome stories of sexual torture and violence" (qtd. in Farr 2000, 28). Seroke's statement shows the failure of the TRC hearings to bring ineffable stories of suffering to light. Wicomb thus attempts to show the failure of the TRC to provide women or, more specifically, soldiers like Dulcie with a voice and platform to address their sexual torture. As Driver (2001) comments, "Dulcie's is the unwritten, pressing story of our times. Dulcie's story is a story of what has not yet been said about violence and betrayal, political commitment and love, about writing and representation and truth" (232). Wicomb's novel is thus not an attempt to show what history has written rather what history has omitted. Since these stories of violence will tarnish the reputation of the ANC and the liberation movement, they cannot be revealed.

Pipic (2017) argues that, in order to uncover "bodies that serve as landscapes of memory", David's Story reviews history. Bodies, particularly female bodies, preserve the memories of a traumatic past, and thus convey a sense of brutality and loss (201). Pipic's statement associates female bodies with traumatic past events. Since women are not given a voice and thus freedom, they are more vulnerable at the hands of the male. Michelle Brown (2008) opines, "Censoring women from the social text makes naturalizing violence against them possible, and David's androcentric recitation cannot obscure the gendered dehumanization that underpins the Movement's opposition to racialized dehumanization" (109). Brown's statement thus hints at the institutionalised violence against women, gendered violence 'underpinning' the attempt to fight racial violence. Brown (2008) again opines that since censorship mutilates the text, the mutilated text tries to hide the mutilated physical body (109).

Dulcie also symbolises the possibility of rape within the anti-apartheid movement. By focusing on the unspeakable story of Dulcie, Wicomb attempts to confront official accounts of history and to undermine the hegemonic perspectives of history. Guerrillas like Dulcie find themselves in a position where they are oppressed by those they are fighting against as well as by those they are fighting for. According to Looche (2008), both Dulcie and Sally not only remain silent about their torture but also seem to have accepted what happened to them

because they grew up in a patriarchal society and are well aware of their helplessness (34). Loocke's statement thus shows the docile upbringing of women in the patriarchal South African society. However, Meg Samuelson (2007) argues that there are more particular reasons behind their silence: "Dulcie complies, veiling her disfigurement beneath clothing that symbolizes her dedication to the cause of freedom and her belief in the necessity of violent struggle to effect it, as well as her refusal to advance this freedom by playing a woman's part" (849). Samuelson thus points out the fact that it is Dulcie's dedication to the movement which compels her to be silent. Being herself a die-hard revolutionary, Dulcie does not want to stigmatise the movement by exposing her victimisation.

RESISTING LINEAR NARRATIVE AND RESHAPING HISTORY

According to Driver (2001), for much of the Griqua history David's major sources are official histories but these incomplete accounts must be supplemented by "stories told to David by his mother, grandmother, and great-grandmother" (226). This statement considers official written history incomplete and seems to focus on the importance of oral tales as a means of finding the truth. Driver (2001) further points out:

It is through the stories of women (by women and about women) that another set of connections opens up between the past and the present, and looking at the text's reinvention of history through the stories of women will allow us to consider the narrator's suggestion that David may be using his interest in Griqua history to displace a memory of the more recent past, and even of what is happening in the present. (226)

It can be deduced from the passage that David is interested in his Griqua origin not only because of his search for origin but also because of his attempt to forget the trauma he has faced as an MK soldier. Driver (2001) also mentions that through women like Krotoä (also known as Eva) and Saartjie Baartman, Wicomb confronts, "the shameful attitudes to body shape that pervade racist South African thinking" (228) since it is "steatopygia"¹ "that has set the story on its course" (Wicomb 2001, 17).

David's Story not only attempts to give the marginalised a voice but also focuses on the difficulties of retrieving history and giving someone a voice. As Driver (2001) points out, "[It] does not try to simply 'give voice' to those who were marginalised, oppressed, and disinherited by colonial and apartheid powers, or those who may now feel (like the Griqua) that they are still silenced. Instead, [it] dramatises the literary, political, philosophical, and ethical issues at stake in any attempt at retrieval of history and voice" (216). Unlike a realist narrative tradition, the novel does not depict the past as chronological and linear but rather fractured and non-linear. There are two parallel narratives of different time-settings, with the use of flashbacks, repetitive and fragmentary language, and even with disruptions to the sense of time, space and identity—which are all the

features of the magical realist narrative. The narrative keeps shifting between past and present, and the reader loses the notion of time and space. The simultaneous existence of two worlds—one dealing with the Griquas and the other the transition period—disrupts the concept of a singular version of reality, and helps the reader compare the past and the present of South Africa and form their own subjective version of the concept of history and nation. The arrival of Dulcie's ghost at the narrator's garden to reveal her ineffable story—since neither David nor the amanuensis were able to piece together her fragmented stories—defies all scientific logic of the world but is considered by the narrator to be an ordinary occurrence, and thus undermines the use of a traditional narrative.

David and the narrator argue over the way Dulcie might be represented. David knows that even if he wants the story of Dulcie to be written down, revealing the secret stories might get him into trouble and destroy the reputation of the movement. Being a woman, the amanuensis, however, wants to reveal the sufferings of Dulcie and with this the traumatising history of women in the history of South Africa. Since Dulcie's story has "no progression in time, no beginning and no end", it cannot be called a "story" (Wicomb 2001, 150). It is made up of "the thin anecdotes, the sorry clutch of hints and innuendos [that] do not lead to anything" (2001, 151). Dulcie's story provides an alternative perspective on narrative, and thus an alternative history, revealing the voice of the marginalised which has been left uncaptured by the official history. However, giving voice to the oppressed is a risky task as the dominant authority is always there to silence it. The attack on the amanuensis' computer with the message "this text deletes itself" (2001, 212) can be considered an attempt by dominant authority to block marginalised voices because the text becomes a threat to the apartheid or oppressive system. In order to protect and preserve the memory of Dulcie, since many people want to erase her story of struggle, we have to save her from disappearing into historical oblivion.

I have mentioned and explained earlier that magical realist narrative possesses the potential to provide characters with relief from distressing events. There is a scene on the penultimate page of the novel which suggests the ways in which magical realist language might possess a healing effect:

Only when I turn to go back to work do I see her sturdy steatopygous form on the central patch of grass, where she has come to sunbathe in private. She is covered with goggas crawling and buzzing all over her syrup sweetness, exploring her orifices, plunging into her wounds; she makes no attempt to wipe the insects away, to shake them off. ... She yawns and stretches in the warm sun. Is this no longer my property? I ask myself. I have never thought of Dulcie as a visitor in my garden. (Wicomb 2001, 212)

The narrator clearly sees Dulcie in her garden with all her bodily wounds. She even describes the goggas explicitly. Although the narrator has never expected to see Dulcie in her garden—this would be impossible as Dulcie is dead—she is not surprised to see her. The unquestioned acceptance of magical events in reality, which is the most prominent feature of magical realism, takes place exactly here.

Since Wicomb fails to represent Dulcie, who is dead, with the help of a realist narrative, she finds an alternative way to represent her by the help of a fragmentary narrative, Dulcie's ghost, African myths, magic and epistemology and, most importantly, imagination.

David's personal way of plotting history can be seen in the Griqua family tree at the start of the book. According to the tree, the first five generations of Kok men have been born without women. The absence of women in the procreation process—a phenomenon that defies the logical order of the universe—also exemplifies the less significant position of women in David's own linear narrative. By allowing David's family tree to stand at the beginning of the novel with all its errors, the narrator silently shows that his one-dimensional and genealogical understanding of history fails to grasp the significance of his historical moment. The narrator thus addresses the necessity of an alternative narrative from the viewpoint of the oppressed in order to provide an approachable version of historical trauma. Magical realist narrative which is non-linear and multi-dimensional has the full potential to be the voice of the oppressed in representing violent historical events.

CONCLUSION

David's story can be considered the 'document of civilization', but its attempt to silence Dulcie's story also makes it a 'document of barbarism'. The employment of two parallel narratives helps David confront the past and his ancestry, and thus repair his torn identity. In spite of his imprisonment at the ANC concentration camp, he still aligns himself with the ideology of the anti-apartheid movement and asks for a narrative which does not include violence and suffering, thus concealing the truth. Although David keeps opposing the inclusion of women in the amanuensis' story, her story in fact defantasises the anti-apartheid movement by revealing the gendered violence and other evils within it, and provides us with an alternative version of history from a female perspective by providing Dulcie and the entire neglected female community a voice.

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